

**THE MOST COMMON GYNECOLOGICAL DISEASES,
EROSIONS IN WOMEN.**

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Abstract: This article discusses the most common gynecological diseases in women, including erosions, their origin, development, clinic and treatment.

Key words: Erosion, Gynecologist, medical manipulation, Heredity.

Relevance of the topic. Cervical erosion (endocervicosis, cervical ectopy) is a violation of the integrity of the mucous membrane in the vaginal part of the organ, defect or covering with wounds. Erosion opens the way for infection to enter the uterus and its appendages and causes the development of chronic inflammatory diseases of the small pelvis, and can even lead to infertility.

At the gynecologist's appointment, almost every second patient is diagnosed with cervical erosion. In general, this disease is one of the most common pathologies in women of childbearing age. The most dangerous complication of uterine erosion is the possibility of its transformation into a low-quality tumor. Therefore, it is very important to detect this disease as soon as possible.

The scientific basis of the subject. There are many causes of pathology and factors that stimulate its development, the main ones are:

- Hormonal disorders and decreased immunity;
- Menstrual cycle disorders;
- Very early onset of sexual life, as well as early pregnancy and childbirth;
- Frequent change of sexual partners;
- Failure to follow personal hygiene;
- Mechanical injuries as a result of difficult childbirth, abortion and other medical manipulations;
- Improper use of vaginal contraceptives or improper rinsing, very rough sex;
- Inflammatory and infectious diseases of the genitourinary system, including their late and incorrect treatment;
- Bacterial and viral diseases;
- Heredity.

The situation with erosion of the cervix is complicated by the fact that this disease does not have clear symptoms and in most cases does not manifest itself at all. But with the development of erosion, patients can identify the following symptoms:

- Discharge of bloody and sometimes purulent discharge between periods, for example, after sexual intercourse;
- Unpleasant-smelling vaginal discharge;
- Menstruation lasts longer than usual, more bleeding;
- Pain in the lower abdomen during urination or sexual intercourse.

In any case, a colposcopy is also performed (examination of the cervix and vagina under magnification) and a smear is taken and analyzed from the surface of the erosion to rule out oncological diseases. Examination of the cervix with an optical device that increases the image by 25-32 times is absolutely painless.

RESEARCH RESULTS. Diagnosis of the pathology is somewhat complicated due to the fact that there is no specific symptom of the disease, and the conditions that cause the patient to complain are not observed.

During the examination of the patient, the gynecologist first examines the cervix using mirrors. As a result, epithelial defects in the form of a bright red spot on the background of healthy tissues, which bleed when in contact with a gynecological instrument, can be identified on its mucous membrane. Depending on the type of erosion, there are other external signs of the disease.

True erosions appear bright pink, areas of dysplasia appear yellow, and atypical foci appear fluid. If mucosal dysplasia is suspected, a biopsy sample is taken from the area and a histological examination is performed.

CONCLUSION. When the disease is detected, it is necessary not to be afraid of it, especially considering that there are many treatment methods available today. Instead, you should be careful about the consequences of not getting treatment on time, because it can lead to various complications before the onset of cancer. Today, erosion is effectively treated, so there is no need to treat it independently at home, to use folk remedies, which, although they seem to be effective, can aggravate the existing situation.

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